

EUROPEAN
COMMISSION

Bruselas, 1.1.202x

COM(2026) xx [PLACEHOLDER]

2026/000x (COD)

Proposal of

DIRECTIVE OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL

On the rights of consumers and the sustainable development in the market of video games

(Directive Stop Destroying Videogames)

(Text with EEA relevance)

{SWD(2026)xxx final}

{Este This text is not an official text elaborated by the European Union or any of their members}

{This text has been drafted by the Citizens' Initiative 000007/2024 Stop Destroying Videogames to propose a working document fully adapted to the legislative formalities and practices of the European Union}

{This is an incomplete and preliminary version, published to reach the general public and European political bodies ahead of the European Commission's response, which is expected by mid-June 2026}

CHAPTER I

GENERAL PROVISIONS

Article 1

Subject Matter and purpose

1. This Directive aims to ensure a high level of consumer protection within the digital single market. To this end, it establishes rules regarding the protection of consumer rights in digital markets, in particular, within the video game market.
2. This Directive complements and clarifies Directive (EU) 2019/770, establishing specific provisions in respect of video games
3. This Directive does not impose on studios, creators, distributors, platforms, or any other responsible parties, nor on any video game industry stakeholder, an obligation to keep their servers perpetually online, or to provide consumers with updates in perpetuity, without prejudice to the legal obligations established in Directives (EU) 2019/770, 2019/771, and 2024/2853; Regulations (EU) 2024/2847, 2022/1925, and 2022/2065; or in any other applicable Union legislative acts.

Article 2

Scope

1. This Directive shall apply to contracts relating to video games concluded between traders or businesses and consumers and users within the territory of the European Union.
2. This Directive shall not apply to:
 - a) activities regulated as gambling;
 - b) video games specifically designed as medical therapies or for skills certification;
 - c) video games offered free of charge (free-to-play) when they do not include alternative monetization systems, pay-to-progress features, or similar modalities.

Article 3

Definitions

1. In the interpretation and definition of this Directive, principles of technological neutrality will be followed, while ensuring a high level of consumer protection.
2. For the purposes of this Directive, the definitions set out in Directive (EU) 2019/770 apply.
3. TBD (if there will be any definitions or not, considering the principle of technological neutrality in law)

Article 4

Sustainable design and prohibition of the destruction or disabling of video games

1. Video games marketed in the European Union shall be designed in a sustainable manner. That is, they must remain in a general working condition after the support period provided by the studio, creator, platform, or any other responsible parties has ended

2. Actions that actively or passively lead to a video game becoming unusable or inaccessible are prohibited.

Article 5
Modalities of compliance

1. The obligations set out in the preceding Article may be fulfilled through any technologies freely chosen by their creators, in accordance with the principle of technological neutrality, provided that they achieve the general objectives established in the precedent article and within this Directive.
2. In particular, creators may fulfill their obligation by effectively implementing any of the following three options:
 - a) Responsible design: in such a way that the video game does not require subsequent support or connection to the company's servers, after support ends. Updates shall solely be limited to what is determined in the contract, and with respect to the basic subjective and objective conformity criteria from Directives (UE) 2019/770 and 2019/771, or any others legally established in other Union legislative acts.
 - b) End-of-life plan: in such a way that there is a publicly available implementation plan for a final update or patch, informed and available to the consumers prior and during to the commercial life of a video game. This final update or patch must enable a general working condition of the video game once the support from the responsible parties ends.
 - c) Right to repair: by providing end-users with sufficiently clear and useful instructions and/or tools to enable them to repair and enjoy the video game by their own means.
3. Compliance with these objectives shall release studios, creators, distributors, platforms, or any other responsible parties from liability.

Article 6
Purchase of the videogame

1. Upon the purchase of a video game or its add-ons, the consumer acquires their copy and the ability to enjoy and retain it within their 'digital environment' in accordance with the principles of technological neutrality; and with the criteria of 'conformity', 'compatibility', 'functionality', and 'interoperability', as established in Directives (EU) 2019/770 and 2019/771.
2. Upon the purchase of a video game, the user does not acquire any intellectual property rights over it (neither economic nor moral), which continue to belong to their legitimate owners and licensees, unless otherwise expressly stipulated in the contract.
3. This Directive does not modify European Union copyright rules or other applicable international treaties. The right of withdrawal of the work from commerce may be exercised by the right holders; however, it does not authorize the withdrawal or destruction of works legitimately acquired by consumers within the territory of the European Union.

Article 7

Rules on the end of official support and the right to repair

1. Sixty days before online services or official support relating to a video game are due to be discontinued, all of the following information items shall be communicated to consumers who have purchased the video game. They shall also be communicated to new consumers who may purchase the video game during that period.
2. The minimum information items are as follows:
 - a) The date on which the online services relating to the video game will cease.
 - b) The services that will no longer be provided.
 - c) The features of the video game that will no longer be available to the purchaser.
 - d) How the purchaser can continue to use the digital game.
 - e) The security risks known at the time of notification that may arise from the cessation of services. A warning regarding potential hazards that may appear after the end of support may also be included.
 - f) Any other items that are relevant to consumers, in accordance with their reasonable expectations and the nature of the video game individually considered.
3. Once official support has ended, consumers shall have the right to repair malfunctions, lacks of conformity, inadequate performance, or any other issues in relation to the hardware or software of the consumer's 'digital environment', as well as to ensure compliance with the concepts of 'compatibility', 'functionality', and 'interoperability' as defined in Articles 2(9), 2(10), 2(11), and 2(12) of Directive (EU) 2019/770 respectively.

Article 8

Prohibition of circumvention practices

1. Any acts carried out by studios, creators, distributors, platforms, or any other responsible parties, as well as any clauses contained in the contract, conducting to the avoidance of the application of this Directive, shall be void.
2. Access to the video game shall not be prohibited to a consumer who has purchased it by reason of a change in the terms and conditions established by studios, creators, distributors, platforms, or any other responsible parties. The consumer shall not be obliged to accept new, more restrictive terms and conditions in order to access content already acquired.

Article *

Right to compensation and liability

1. TBD.
2. Where the trader is liable to the consumer because of any failure to comply with this Directive, or because of a lack of compliance resulting from an act or omission by a company, trader or person in previous links of the chain of transactions, the trader shall be entitled to pursue remedies against the person or persons liable in the chain of commercial transactions. The person against whom the trader may pursue remedies, and the relevant actions and conditions of exercise, shall be determined by national law.

Article 10
Mandatory nature

1. Unless otherwise provided for in this Directive, any contractual term which, to the detriment of the consumer, excludes the application of the national measures transposing this Directive, derogates from or varies the effects of such measures before the failure to supply or the lack of conformity is brought to the trader's attention by the consumer, or is otherwise contrary to the measures provided for in this Directive, shall not be binding on the consumer..
2. This Directive shall not prevent the trader from offering the consumer contractual arrangements that go beyond the protection provided for in this Directive.

Article 10
Review

No later than five years after the date of application of this Directive, and every five years thereafter, the Commission shall carry out a review of this Directive and submit a report on its main findings to the European Parliament, to the Council, and to the European Economic and Social Committee. The evaluation might, where appropriate, inform a proposal for the amendment or repeal of this Directive in light of legal, technical, or economic developments.

Article 11
Transposition

By 1 July 202x at the latest, Member States shall adopt and publish the measures necessary to comply with this Directive. They shall immediately inform the Commission thereof.

They shall apply those measures from 1 January 202x.

When Member States adopt those measures, they shall contain a reference to this Directive or be accompanied by such a reference on the occasion of their official publication. Member States shall determine how such reference is to be made.

Member States shall communicate to the Commission the text of the main provisions of national law which they adopt in the field covered by this Directive.

Article 12
Entry into force and application

1. This Directive shall enter into force on the twentieth day following that of its publication in the *Official Journal of the European Union*.
2. It shall apply from 1 January 202X (TBD).
3. It shall not apply retroactively to video games marketed before 1 January 202X.

Article 13
Destinataries

This Directive is addressed to the Member States.

Done in Brussels, xxxxxxx 202x.

For the European Parliament _____ *For the Council*
The President _____ *The President*

WORK IN PROGRESS DOCUMENT . NOT FINAL. V 0.21 26.05.2026